

FEMALE ENZYME IN THE SOCIAL STRATIFICATION OF SOCIETY IN THE FIRST THIRD OF THE XX CENTURY: TRADITION AND TRANSFORMATION

Mamatkarimov Ilyasbek Bakhritdin

Graduate student of NamSU

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Annotatsion: The article reveals the topic of the female enzyme in the social stratification of society in the first third of the 20th century: tradition and transformation. And also the author reveals the role and position of women in society and an overview of the topic of the historical stage from the point of view of the modern period.

Keywords: attitude towards woman, the role of women in society, womens rights, benefits for women, womens club, colonial period, soviet period.

The biggest goal before us today is to create innovations in society and make profound qualitative changes in all areas. It consists of modernization and reform of socio-political and economic life. The realization of this goal is based on the implementation of changes in the thinking of citizens, increasing their social activity, raising political culture, and ultimately the formation of a sense of responsibility for what is happening in society. All this will not happen without strengthening the spiritual foundations of society.

Thanks to national independence, there is an opportunity to critically observe the history of the Soviet period, distorted in the historiography of our people, from the point of view of the ideology of national independence on the basis of a new and objective approach. The need to restore the true history of the Uzbek people and arm the people with the truth of this history has become a topical issue. It has always been known that "we must restore our true history, arm our people and our nation with this history" [1]. The head of our state Sh. M. As Mirziyoyev said: "Now is the time, even if we restore this history from the eightieth century, and if we convey this scientific basis to the people, it will be enlightenment." Because the comparison of the history of the colonial and Soviet periods, studied in the rise of the spirituality of our people, with the current period of independence allows us to more properly appreciate our independence [2]. Today, however, true history must be studied objectively on a scientific basis.

The issue of women has always been closely linked to the problems of the nation, its history, present and future. That is why it was said, "We know a nation not by its name, but by its culture and spirituality, and we look at the

roots of history." [3] "The cultural level of any society on earth is determined by its attitude towards women," says Sh.M. Mirziyoev [4].

Therefore, the issue of ensuring the rights and interests of women in Uzbekistan, the creation of decent working and living conditions for them, the realization of their abilities and potential has risen to the level of state policy in the country. It is also important that "the problems of history and culture can be truly understood only when studied together, in a logical harmony, because history is the basis of national spirituality" [5].

At the current stage of social development, it is very important to make a general analysis of the situation of women in Uzbekistan during the Soviet dictatorship and draw conclusions from it. The scientific analysis of the mechanism of the accumulation of national and spiritual values in the first 30 years of the twentieth century, the emergence of depression among the population, the further improvement of administrative methods of governing the political, social and cultural spheres is very important for today's cultural and spiritual processes.

The question of the attitude of the colonial and Soviet authorities towards the women of the indigenous peoples is also one of the important problems awaiting its scientifically based interpretation. This is because the attitude of the colonial and Soviet authorities to the "female enzyme in the social stratification of society in the first thirty years of the twentieth century: tradition and change", which was the subject of the study, was very contradictory in nature. Therefore, the main task today is to scientifically substantiate and objectively cover the historical reality with the help of sources, "trying to understand the essence of the period" [6]. Indeed, the study of Tsarist Russia and the attitude of the Soviet government towards women and the female enzyme in the social stratification of society at that time: tradition and change is necessary not only from a scientific point of view, but also because of the social order of society.

The problems of the nation have always been closely connected with its history, present and future. Throughout the long history of our country, the role of women in the life of the state and society has been significant. History has not forgotten the work of women in politics, economics, spirituality and culture. Many generations of humanity have considered it their ultimate goal to make women free and equal. The great thinkers and progressives of the past have raised the issue of the emancipation of women. However, in an exploitative society, women could not and would not be free and equal [7]. This issue has been resolved due to independence, and now the issue before our researchers is the need to scientifically study the activities of our women at that time.

At the current stage of social development, it is important to make a general analysis of the social status of women in the Russian Empire and the former Soviet Turkestan, and draw conclusions from it. We believe that the development of society today is very important for advanced socio-cultural processes. For the Republic of Uzbekistan, where 49.8% of the population [8] and a significant part of the labor force are women, their role in social life, status, level of activity, development of spiritual and historical values and their role in the formation of new values is one of the most important factors. This is the basis of the ongoing socio-political, economic and spiritual reforms. Reforms encompass all aspects of public life, leaving unresolved but unresolved pressing issues. Women also have a role to play in solving these problems. As the ongoing process of socio-political, economic and spiritual reforms requires the active participation of women, the issue of treatment of women has risen to the level of public policy. Therefore, the government pays special attention to "increasing the socio-political activity of women in full compliance with the democratic changes taking place in our country, their role and prestige in solving the tasks of family, society and state building [9]." In particular, the proclamation of 1999 as the "Year of Women", the historic decree of March 17, 1999 "On additional measures to strengthen the social protection of women", the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Additional Privileges for Women", proclamation of 2000 as the Year of Healthy Generation, 2001 as the Year of Mothers and Children, May 25, 2004 Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of June 30, 2004 on the implementation of the Action Strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Youth Support and Public Health" In accordance with the state program "March 5, 2021" Women's activities in Uzbekistan Proof of our opinion is the resolution "On the program of measures to ensure the implementation of Decree No. PF-5020" on measures to further improve the system of ensuring their active participation in public life.

Also, the call to make the activities of women's public councils in the country a real representative and defender of women's interests, a real integral part of the free civil society we are building is another expression of respect and great confidence in women in our country [10]. Because, "the extent to which society has advanced on the path of democratic change, the attitude of this society towards women determines its cultural and spiritual level" [11]. Therefore, the study of the period under study also serves to learn exemplary lessons, to understand the events of the present period. In particular, in the

words of the head of our state, "In order to choose the right path in difficult situations, when the fate of the homeland and the nation is decided, it is necessary to know the history and the bitterness of life." In this context, it can be said that the historical study of the attitude of the Soviet government towards women is of great scientific, theoretical and economic-practical importance, which confirms the relevance of the research topic.

Like the colonial system of the Tsarist period, the closed colonialism of the Soviet era was perceived by the indigenous people as a heavy colonial yoke that undermined their traditions, customs and way of life. Therefore, in the second half of the XIX century - early XX century, the national liberation movement was aimed at getting rid of the yoke of colonialism, gaining freedom, the establishment of national statehood on the basis of restoring the national values of Eastern civilization [12]. The place and role of girls in society is described in terms of class. Since the assessment given to them is almost illegal, it is necessary to study this period in depth and give it a fair assessment. This determines the relevance of the study and research of the topic.

The first thirty years of the twentieth century cover the years 1900-1930. This period in the history of Uzbekistan, including Tsarist Russia and the Soviet regime, in the history of women's activities in the socio-economic and cultural life of society, is marked by the objective flaws of its one-party Soviet state-political system. Given the nature of the aggressive policy of the colonial system in Turkestan in the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the egocentric flaws in the relationship between the center and the region, and the Soviet government's treatment of Uzbek women, this issue can be divided into three stages. The first phase covers the years 1900-1917. To analyze that during this period tsarism used violence as a universal tool to solve all the problems in the country, and that this phenomenon is a characteristic feature of the colonial regime created by tsarism. The colonial apparatus was constantly expanded and strengthened with the issuance of various decrees, resolutions and directives confirming the real dominance of tsarism in all vital spheres of Turkestan society.

The colonial program of moral oppression of the local population focused on the study of Russian women in the region. He also advocated for women to switch to the Russian way of life, to have an Orthodox influence on the upbringing of their children, to get rid of the oppression of the veil, and to "open up", which had a negative effect. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov noted: "This negative consequence was several times greater than the consequences of imported civilization" [13].

The second phase covers the years 1917-1925. During this period, the first steps were taken to involve women in the socio-economic life of Uzbekistan and to raise their culture, free from the pressure of the ruling ideology. Social organizations such as women's departments, trade unions, komsomol organizations, cooperatives, the Koshchi association, and women's clubs, which emerged as part of the political system, have taken "initiatives" to involve women in socio-economic and cultural life.

The third stage covers the years 1925-1930, in which the idea of literally equalizing the labor of women and men predominated. As a result of the "Attack" campaign in 1926-1927, the attitude towards women changed significantly. The company, a guide to the revolutionary changes that had begun in the social, economic, and cultural spheres of society, treated the women of the indigenous peoples by chauvinistic administrative means out of self-interest. Especially during the period of industrialization, collectivization and cultural change that began in the country, based on the prevailing ideology and the pressure and demands of the state, women's broad participation in changes in socio-economic and cultural life was achieved only in form and number. However, this process concealed the false idea of internationalism, which denied any national identity and promoted a "single Soviet people", which in turn allowed Uzbek women to cultivate their supporters who believed in the "ideas of socialism" for the dictatorship. Contrary to this stage, women, whose social and political activity had increased, became victims of the repressive policies of the dictatorial regime in the late 1930s. All this shows the importance of studying the complex, multifaceted processes of the above-mentioned period from a historical point of view and demonstrates the scientific, theoretical, practical and political significance of the issue.

The level of study of the subject shows the conclusion of historiography that this topic has not yet been studied in terms of a new worldview, the ideology of the national orator as an independent object of scientific knowledge. Also, some aspects of the topic have been studied separately and studied scientifically as a whole. The scientific literature used in the study is divided into two chronological periods:

1. Colonial and Soviet research.
2. Post-independence scientific research of Uzbekistan.

The study of the level of women's freedom in Uzbekistan is of particular importance. Indeed, this victory serves as a model for many nations that have achieved national independence and are on the path of non-capitalist development.

Therefore, this issue has always been in the focus of researchers. This is the reason for the great diversity and diversity of literature on the problem, from women's and popular literature, to memoirs, to monographs, to statistical research. This indicates that it is time to study the issue historiographically and that it is very important to do so [14].

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